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VERBAL NOUN OR VERBAL ADJECTIVE?

THE CASE OF THE LATIN GERUNDIVE AND GERUND

Martin Haspelmath

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Contents

1. The aim of this paper	2
2. Gerundive and gerund	
2.1. The nd-form	3
2.2. Traditional grammar	3
2.3. The gerund	4
2.4. The gerundive	6
3. The naa-infinitive in Hindi	
3.1. The parallel with the gerundive	8
3.2. The parallel with the gerund	11
4. The identity of the gerund and the impersonal gerundive	11
5. From verbal adjective to infinitive: Latin and Hindi	
5.1. Classical Latin	13
5.2. The reanalysis in Latin	14
5.3. The reanalysis in Hindi	17
6. On the question of historical priority	18
7. How can an adjective acquire propositional meaning?	
7.1. The problem	20
7.2. A cognitively-based approach	21
7.3. Application to the gerundive	23
7.4. Degrees of syntacticization	25
Notes	27
References	32

1. The aim of this paper

It is the aim of this paper to present and elaborate a new solution to the old syntactic problems connected with the Latin gerundive and gerund, two verbal categories which have been interpreted variously either as adjective (or participle) or noun (or infinitive). These questions have been much discussed for quite a number of years (cf., among others, Aalto 1949, Tovar 1950, Hahn 1965, 1966, Neschke 1974, Blümel 1979, Stepanov 1985), but for the most part from a philological or purely diachronic point of view. All these linguists try to explain the peculiarities of these categories and their syntax by showing that the gerund is historically prior to the gerundive.

Our point of departure is Risch 1984, who traces in detail the development of the syntax of these forms from Old Latin through to the post-classical period, and arrives at the opposite conclusion. Risch's primary concern is to provide a philological confirmation of his hypothesis of the historical priority of the gerundive over the gerund. We rely on his work (which in terms of philological profundity stands out among the other publications on this topic) and concentrate on the syntactic questions, which Risch deals with only in passing and not very clearly.

It is our thesis (following Risch) that in order to arrive at a unified account of gerundive and gerund we do not have to go back to prehistoric times. Even for the classical language gerund and gerundive represent the same category, in the sense that the gerund can be shown to be a special case of the gerundive. Additional evidence from a parallel construction in Hindi is adduced to make the Latin facts more plausible. It is only in the post-classical language that certain tendencies which had shown up already in Old Latin poetry become stronger and finally lead to a reanalysis of the gerundive and a split into two distinct syntactic constructions.

The propositional meaning of the gerundive in its attributive use is explained with reference to a conflict between syntactic and cognitive principles. Special constructions which are the effects of such conflicts can be found in other parts of grammar.

Languages differ with respect to the degree of syntacticization (or conventionalization) of these special constructions.

2. Gerundive and gerund

2.1. The nd-form

There exists in Latin a peculiar non-finite verbal inflectional category which exhibits a complex syntactic behavior: in some cases it looks more like a verbal noun (and accordingly inflects for case in the singular), in others it rather seems to be a sort of passive participle (and accordingly inflects for the agreement-dimensions case, number and gender). In the former case it is called the gerund, in the latter the gerundive. Formally, however, we are clearly dealing with one and the same category, cf. an example of the gerundive in (1), and one of the gerund in (2).

(1) leg-end-us, -a, -um
read-GER -M F N
"that is to be read"

(2) leg-end-i, -o, -um, -o
read-GER-GEN DAT ACC ABL
"of reading, for reading, etc."

Obviously, the only difference is the different inflectional options. So on the basis of its formal characteristics, we can call this category simply the nd-form.

2.2. Traditional grammar

In traditional grammar, gerund and gerundive are treated as two completely distinct categories which really are not related to each other and should under no circumstances be confused. Cf. Hofmann & Szantyr 1965:§201:

"Das Gerundium erfüllt die Funktion eines Verbalsubstantivs, das den Infinitiv in den obliquen Kasus ergänzt...und ähnlich wie dieser verbale Rektion aufweist: legendi librum wie legere librum... Das Gerundivum ist nach herkömmlicher Auffassung, ähn-

lich wie griech. φιλητέος, ein Verbaladjektiv, das nachträglich gleich dem to-Partizip in das Verbalsystem eingegliedert wurde."¹

2.3. The gerund

When the nd-form is used as a sort of nominalized or rather inflected infinitive, it is called gerund. In most cases it can be translated by an English gerund and is represented in the following table, together with the infinitive:

	INFINITIVE	GERUND	
NOM	legere		"to read"
GEN		legendi	"of reading"
DAT		legendo	"for reading"
ACC	legere		"to read"
		legendum	"reading"
ABL		legendo	"by reading"

The infinitive proper is used only in the direct cases, that is when governed by a verb.² Here two cases can be distinguished: (A) as subject of "impersonal predicates", see ex. (3), and (B) as object of the usual "complement-taking verbs" (for this term cf. Noonan 1985), see ex. (4).

(3) hunc librum legere utile est
 this book read:INF useful is
 "It is useful to read this book."

(4) cupio hunc librum legere
 I-wish this book read:INF
 "I wish to read this book."

In cases where the infinitive would have to be governed by a non-verb (that is noun, adjective or preposition), the gerund is used instead:

N: (5) potestas respondendi
 possibility answer:GER:GEN "the possibility of answering"
 (6) ars gubernandi
 art govern:GER:GEN "the art of governing"
 A: (7) homines bellandi cupidi
 men fight:GER:GEN desirous "men, desirous of waging war"

P: (8) in legendo
 in read:GER:ABL "in/while reading"
 (9) ad vivendum
 to live:GER:ACC "for living"

The nouns and adjectives which are used in this way are often derived from complement-taking verbs or at least have a similar meaning that requires a propositional actant (=complement), e.g. potestas "possibility, power" (cf. possum "I am able"), cupidus "desirous" (cf. cupio "I desire"). They can be called "complement-taking nouns (and adjectives)".

The gerund can also be used in the ablative case without a preposition, and very rarely in the dative case. Here the gerund is not governed by the verb, but modifies it adverbially.

ADV: (10) (DAT:) scribundo adfuisse (Cic.Att.4,17,12)
 write:GER:DAT be-present
 "to be present in order to write"
 (11) (ABL:) Romanus sedendo vincit (Varro RR 1,2,2)
 Roman settle:GER:ABL conquers
 "The Roman conquers by settling."

Although this last-mentioned use is not normally taken to be an instance of complementation, we will use the term complementation (or complement function) as a cover term for the functions of the gerund.

Like the infinitive, the gerund behaves more like a verb than a noun in that it takes adverbial modifiers. So we have (12) with a gerund, which is in clear contrast to (13) with a verbal noun.

(12) ars bene gubernandi
 art well govern:GER:GEN "the art of governing well"
 (13) ars bonae gubernationis
 art good government:GEN "the art of good government"

In the same way, the accusative object is not changed to genitive as it is with verbal nouns. Note, however, that in the classical language the gerund is used transitively very rarely, a fact that will become more important later (cf. 3.1.).³

2.4. The gerundive

When the nd-form agrees with a noun in case, number and gender like an adjective or participle, either in attributive or predicative position, it is called gerundive. The gerundive has two rather different meanings, according to the syntactic function it fulfills. At first sight these two meanings do not seem to have much in common.

2.4.1. Predicative use. When the gerundive is used predicatively (=as a predicate nominal), it has a passive and modal meaning, in most cases that of necessity or obligation, more rarely that of future time reference. Examples:

- (14) fugienda semper injuria est (Cic.off.1,25)
flee:GER:NOM.F.SG always injustice(F) is
"Injustice should always be avoided."
- (15) si quis quid reddit, magna habenda 'st gratia (Ter.Ph.56)
if who what returns great have:GER:NOM.F.SG is gratefulness(F)
"If anybody returns anything, one should be grateful."

The agent may be added in the dative case:

- (16) Caesari erant transcendendae valles maximae (Caes.bc 1,68,2)
Caesar:DAT were overcome:GER:NOM.F.PL valleys(F) very=large
"Caesar had to overcome very large valleys."
- (17) uxor tibi ducenda 'st, Pamphile, hodie (Ter.And.254)
wife you:DAT lead:GER:NOM.F.SG is Pamphilus today
"You have to take a wife today, Pamphilus."

In most school grammars the corresponding attributive use is mentioned, also with passive and modal meaning, e.g.

- (18) liber legendus
book(M) read:GER:NOM.M.SG "A book that is to be read."

However, this use is extremely limited. In the classical period, it occurs only with verbs of emotion (etc.) in prose (cf. (19) and (20)) and is more widespread only in poetry (cf.(21)), see Risch 1984:8.3.

- (19) mirandum in modum gaudeo (Cic.fam.15,8)
marvel:GER:ACC:N:SG in manner(N):ACC.SG I=rejoice
"I am tremendously pleased."(lit."in a way that is to be marveled at"

- (20) non contemnendam manum in ultionem domini compararat (Svet.Tib.25)
not despise:GER:ACC.F.SG gang(F):ACC in revenge lord:GEN s/he=had-brought-together
"He had organized a considerable gang for the revenge of his lord."
- (21) o sol pulcher, o laudande (Hor.carm. 4,2,45)
o sun(M):VOC.SG beautiful o praise:GER:VOC.M.SG
"O beautiful sun, the one who has to be praised!"

2.4.2. Attributive use. When the gerundive is used attributively, in most cases there is no modal meaning involved and we are dealing with a quite different phenomenon: the gerundive construction ("Gerundivkonstruktion"). An NP consisting of a noun and an attributive gerundive which together form a gerundive construction does not refer to a thing but to a state of affairs: it has propositional meaning. Thus, the gerundive construction is a peculiar technique for nominalizing clauses in which the verb does not become a verbal noun and head of the resulting NP, as in the usual case, but is made into a verbal adjective which stands in an attributive relation to the underlying direct object. Examples:

- N: (22) spes potiendorum castrorum (Caes. bG 3,6,2)
hope take:GER:GEN.PL.N camp(N):GEN.PL
"the hope of taking the camp"
- A: (23) homines belli gerendi peritissimi (Cic.Font.43)
men war(N):GEN.SG wage:GER:GEN.SG.N very-experienced
"men, very experienced in waging war"
- P: (24) de captivis commutandis Romam missus est (Cic.off.1,35)
for captives(M):ABL.PL exchange:GER:ABL.PL.M to=Rome sent is
"He was sent to Rome in order to exchange prisoners."
- (25) impediendae reliquae munitionis causa (Caes.bc 1,82,1)
hinder:GER:GEN.SG.F remaining supplies(F):GEN.SG for-the-sake
"for the sake of hindering the rest of the supplies"
- ADV:(26) (ABL:) noster populus sociis defendendis terrarum omnium potitus est
our nation allies(M):ABL.PL defend:GER..countries all conquered is
"Our nation has conquered all countries by defending the allies."
- (27) (DAT:) hibernis oppugnandis hunc esse dictum diem (Caes.bG 5,27,5)
winter-quarters:DAT.PL attack:GER:DAT.PL this be said day
"that this day was fixed for attacking the winter quarters"

These two meanings look very different and hard to unify. On the other hand, the attributive use of the gerundive (i.e. the gerundive construction) immediately strikes one as very similar, and practically identical with that of the gerund. Both the range of

syntactic contexts (government by lexical categories other than verbs and adverbial modification) and the meaning (state of affairs) are exactly the same. Indeed one can say that the gerundive supplements the gerund in its transitive use and has the same complement function here.

Various accounts of this situation have been proposed, and it is interesting to note that a transformational description which derives the gerundive construction from the gerund appears even in traditional grammars. This transformation, of course, does not have any theoretical significance, and is used essentially as a pedagogical device. Cf. the following quotation from a pedagogical grammar (Menge 1953:§449):

(Das Gerundium wird in das "Gerundivum verwandelt, d.h. das Objekt wird in den Kasus des Gerundiums gesetzt und das Gerundivum mit demselben in Übereinstimmung gebracht: In persequendis hostibus (aus: in persequendo hostes); ad liberandam patriam (aus: ad liberandum patriam)..."⁴

Such a way of describing the Latin facts may be appropriate for didactic purposes, but more arguments supporting this analysis are required if one assumes that this transformation is linguistically real, either as a synchronic rule (Neschke 1974) or as a diachronic change (Aalto 1949, Hahn 1965, Blümel 1979). See below (6.) for more discussion of the diachronic development.

A clue to a more adequate analysis of the data comes from an unexpected direction. In Hindi one finds a rather similar situation, to which we turn now.

3. The naa-infinitive in Hindi

3.1. The parallel with the gerundive

There is an infinitive in Hindi which is marked by a suffix -naa and is used as a direct object of complement-taking verbs such as "begin" (šuruu karnaā), "stop" (khatam karnaā), "want" (caahnaā). (The examples are taken from Pořizka 1972 and Fairbanks & Misra 1966; cf. also Meile 1948)

- (28) māī phal khaa-naa šuruu kar-taa hūū
I fruit eat - INF beginning do-PRES COP.1.SG
"I begin eating fruit."
(29) voo ghar jaa-naa caah-taa hai
he home go - INF want-PRES COP.3.SG
"He wants to go home."

Furthermore, it occurs as subject of the impersonal modal expression caahiyee "it is necessary" (cf. (30)) and, as predicate together with the copula, with the meaning of necessity or obligation (cf. (31)).

- (30) mujhee yee kaam kar-naa caahiyee
for-me this work do - INF it-is-necessary
"I ought to do this job."
(31) mujhe makkhan khariid-naa hai
for-me butter buy - INF COP.3.SG
"I have to buy butter."

This last construction brings to mind the Latin predicative gerundive with the same meaning of necessity, but at this point the comparison does not yet seem necessary. After all, very similar constructions appear in other languages as well, with the infinitive taking on a meaning of necessity in certain syntactic environments, cf. the Russian example in (32):

- (32) mne kupit' maslo
for-me buy:INF butter "I have to buy butter."

In many languages the infinitive seems to possess a sort of inherent modal meaning, and it is not very unusual to find it in an impersonal construction with a "morally responsible agent" (Lyons 1977:823) in the dative case. Cf. Strunk 1977:28ff. for more examples from other Indo-European languages.

But the following property of the Hindi infinitive is striking: it agrees with its direct object in gender and number, as can be seen from (33)-(34).

- (33) māī rooṭii khaa-nii šuruu kar-taa hūū
I bread(F) eat-INF.F.SG beginning do - PRES COP.1.SG
"I begin eating bread."
(34) voo kamr-ee deekh-nee caah-taa hai
he room(M)-PL see - INF.M.PL want - PRES COP.3.SG
"He wants to see the rooms."

This type of agreement is very unusual cross-linguistically. Normally, verbs agree with their direct objects only in person, see Lehmann 1982. But if we translate these sentences into Latin, using the gerundive construction, we see a very similar pattern:

(35)(tr.of(33)) panis edendi initium facio (=panem edere incipio)
bread(M):GEN.SG eat:GER:GEN.SG.M beginning I-do

(36)(tr.of(34)) camerarum videndarum cupidus est (=cameras videre cupit)
rooms:GEN.PL see:GER:GEN.PL desirous is

In both languages there is agreement of the direct object with the non-finite verb (infinitive in Hindi, gerundive in Latin) instead of verbal government. The only difference is that this construction has a wider distribution in Hindi and is not limited to the oblique cases like the Latin gerundive.⁵ It occurs also (and primarily) as direct object, a position in which the Latin gerundive cannot appear. This is why in translating (33) and (34) into Latin we have to use a nominal paraphrase to get the desired effect. (As a consequence, the Latin sentences (35)-(36) are rather artificial; the more natural equivalents with infinitives are indicated in parentheses.)

Now the similarity is not restricted to the complement function of the Latin gerundive. The predicative function with modal meaning is also paralleled by the Hindi infinitive, as we have already noted, cf. (31). Here too the infinitive agrees with its direct object in gender and number.

(37) mujhee khabar bheej-nii hai
for-me message(F) send - INF.F.SG COP.3.SG
"I have to send a message."

The exact Latin equivalent of this sentence would be:

(38) mihi nuntius mittendus est⁶
I:DAT message(M) send:GER:NOM.SG.M IS

Thus, the Hindi infinitive provides a striking parallel with the Latin gerundive which extends to both the attributive and the predicative functions of 2.4. This is a strong argument for the unity of these functions in Latin, too.

3.2. The parallel with the gerund

The Hindi infinitive now illuminates also the relationship of the gerund to both functions of the gerundive. If the infinitive is used without a direct object with which it could agree, i.e. if the verb is used intransitively, the Hindi infinitive has the unmarked form, which is identical to the masculine singular agreement form.

(39) ham cal-naa caah-tee hãĩ
we walk - INF(.M.SG) walk-PRES COP.1.PL
"We want to walk around."

The same analysis turns out to be applicable to the Latin gerund: it is nothing other than the unmarked form of the gerundive, which has, as expected, neuter singular form in Latin. The distribution of agreeing and non-agreeing forms in Latin is exactly analogous to their distribution in Hindi, a fact that has not received sufficient attention so far. The agreeing construction (gerundive) is used when the verb is used transitively while the non-agreeing construction (gerund) is used when the verb is intransitive or used intransitively and hence there is nothing for the nd-form to agree with. Again we can translate (35) directly into Latin by using the nd-form, and what we get now is the gerund:

(40) ambulandi cupidinem habemus (=ambulare cupimus)
walk:GER:GEN(.SG.N) desire we-have

The gerund is thus only a special case of the gerundive. It is a gerundive without a direct object to agree with.

4. The identity of the gerund and the impersonal gerundive

A moment ago we noted that the gerund is nothing other than the unmarked form of the gerundive and that it is employed when the verb is used intransitively. When the verb is used transitively, however, the gerundive agrees with its (underlying) direct object. But recall that the Latin gerundive has passive meaning (at least in its predicative use) and the underlying direct object surfaces as subject. So from the point of view of Latin we would have to say that the unmarked form is used

when there is no subject, and we can call the gerund the impersonal form (=passive form without a subject) of the gerundive.

We can see this more clearly if we convert the gerundive construction into its finite counterpart, as in (42) from (41).

(41) superstitione tollenda religio non tollitur (Cic.div.2,148)
superstition(F):ABL.SG abolish:GER:ABL.SG.F religion not abolish:PASS.3.SG
"By abolishing superstition religion is not abolished."

(42) superstitio tollitur "superstition is abolished"
superstition abolish:PASS.3.SG

The resulting finite clause (42) is passive, of course. Likewise, if we convert a gerund into its finite counterpart, we get a passive clause, as in (44) from(43).

(43) equitandi laus (Cic.Tusc.2,62)
ride:GER:GEN(.SG.N) praise "the praise of riding"

(44) equitatur "One rides./There is riding going on."
ride:PASS.3.SG

But this time, of course, the passive clause is impersonal. Impersonal passives are a very common phenomenon in Latin and we should therefore not be surprised to find impersonal gerundives too.

Now the impersonal gerundive does not occur only in attributive position (or complement-function), but also in predicative position with modal meaning, cf. (45)-(46) (Risch 1984:\$46,\$114).

(45) paci semper consulendum est (Cic.off.1,35)
peace always plan:GER:NOM(.SG.N) is
"One should always strive for peace."

(46) clam illuc redeundum est mihi (Plt.Amph.527)
secretly thither return:GER:NOM(.SG.N) is I:DAT
"I must return there in secret."

Although this is, like the gerund, an impersonal use of the gerundive, this use of the nd-form has traditionally not been called gerund but simply "impersonal gerundive". The reason for this terminological inconsistency is that either one of two sufficient criteria is taken to be sufficient for classification as gerundive: (A) modal meaning or (B) agreeing form. The result is that no single sufficient criterion for the gerund is left, and it can only be defined ex negativo by a conjunction of two necessary

criteria, namely non-agreeing neuter form and propositional non-modal meaning.

In the following table the four syntactic uses of the nd-form are represented:

	impersonal (neuter form)	personal (agreeing form)
complement function (propositional meaning)	ars gubernandi	spes potiendorum castrorum
predicative function (modal meaning)	paci consulendum est	fugienda injuria est

Along the axes the basic classificatory features are given with the criteria for assignment added in parentheses. Everything falling into the shaded area is traditionally referred to as gerundive. The inappropriateness of this terminology should be obvious. It seems that the most reasonable alternative is to identify the traditional terms gerund and gerundive with the impersonal and personal uses, respectively. The nd-forms in (45) and (46) would be called gerunds according to this convention.⁷

5. From verbal adjective to infinitive: Latin and Hindi

5.1. Classical Latin

The explanation given in section 3. for the syntax of the gerund presupposes that the distinction between agreeing gerundive and non-agreeing gerund coincides with that between transitive and intransitive use of the verb. However, the coincidence is not complete and consequently our analysis requires a certain amount of idealization of the data.

As a rule, in classical Latin (Cicero, Caesar) the gerundive goes together with transitive use, while the gerund goes together with intransitive use of the verb. Cf. Risch 1984:\$101:

"(Beim Gerundium) wird im klassischen Latein bekanntlich ein Akkusativobjekt im ganzen gemieden und stattdessen die Gerundivkonstruktion verwendet."^{8,9}

This rule, however, has certain stylistically motivated exceptions. The gerund plus accusative object can be used instead of the gerundive construction,

(A) if the accusative object is a neuter pronoun, e.g.

(47) cupiditas agendi aliquid (Cic.fin.5,55)
desire do:GER:GEN(.SG.N) something:ACC
"the desire to do something"

The obvious motivation here is that in the genitive case it would be impossible to distinguish neuter pronouns from masculine pronouns.

(B) if the accusative object is a personal pronoun, e.g.

(48) cupidus sum te audiendi (Cic.de orat.2,16)
desirous I-am you:ACC hear:GER:GEN(.SG.N)
"I wish to hear you."

The genitive case of personal pronouns would be a bit awkward as it is rarely used (with pronouns, the possessive adjective is used in most cases where the genitive case is required).

(C) if the gerundive construction would be in the genitive plural, e.g.

(49) spatium pila in hostis coiciendi (Caes. bG 1,52,3)
space spears in enemy throw:GER:GEN(.SG.N)
"space for throwing spears at the enemy"

In this way the cacophony of two successive endings -orum (or -arum) is avoided.

(D) in a number of minor cases, cf. Risch 1984:98, Hofmann & Szantyr 1965:§202 Cb, Menge 1953:§449.¹⁰

5.2. The reanalysis in Latin

In post-classical Latin the use of the gerund with an accusative object is becoming more and more frequent (Risch 1984:§104), cf. (50):

(50) (Hannibal) mutando nunc vestem, nunc tegumenta capitis...
Hannibal change:GER:ABL now dress now coverings head:GEN
sese ab insidiis munierat (Liv.22,1,3)
himself from ambushes s/he-had-protected

"Hannibal had protected himself against ambushes by changing now his dress, now his hats."

Such clauses occur, though still rather restricted, as early as in Old Latin poetry (Risch 1984:§126-27). We may assume that in the colloquial language (which is reflected to a greater extent in Old Latin poetry than in classical prose) the reanalysis was made earlier and that in classical times the system described here was valid only for the written language. It is very probable that the classical language preserves an archaism here and that this system was valid for the colloquial language at some earlier period, but nothing definite can be said for lack of documentation.

It appears, however, that the gerundive construction was never used as extensively as the Hindi infinitive, since the Latin infinitive in -re/-ri/-i/-ier always existed side by side with the gerundive and fulfilled the more central functions, while the gerundive construction was used only to supplement the infinitive in the more peripheral functions as a dependent of prepositions and nouns, where the infinitive could not appear.

Be that as it may, it is clear that at some point in the history of Latin a reanalysis of the gerundive took place: The former impersonal and passive verbal adjective is reanalyzed as an active infinitive-like verbal noun. Now it becomes a rule that the direct object object of transitive verbs is in the accusative case and the gerund is used. The gerundive in complement-function (=the gerundive construction) loses its place within the system and is used only as a reminiscence of the classical norm and not in virtue of its contemporary place in the system. In the new system the adjectival gerundive and the infinitive-like gerund are clearly separated now and have nothing in common. In the popular language survive only the gerund, mainly in its adverbial use, and some isolated gerundives which had become lexicalized already in the classical period (Risch 1984:B.4.a). After this reanalysis we no longer have a unitary category, but

two completely distinct categories: the passive-modal verbal adjective and the "declinable infinitive", now used transitively and intransitively like the infinitive proper. What was formerly the (non-impersonal) gerundive construction is now outside the system and a really strange phenomenon, sharing properties of both the declinable infinitive (complement function) and of the passive-modal verbal adjective (agreement with its head noun). The reanalysis can be diagrammed as follows:

	gerund (impersonal)	gerundive (personal)
complement function	ars gubernandi	spes potiendorum castrorum
predicative function	paci consulendum est	fugienda injuria est

↓ reanalyzed as

declinable
infinitive
(complement f.)

intransitive	ars gubernandi
transitive	spes potiendi castra

passive-modal
verbal adjective
(predicative function)

impersonal	personal
consulendum est	fugienda injuria est

While in the original system the chief criterion for classification was impersonal or personal use of the verbal adjective, now the chief criterion is the external syntactic function (complement or predicative).

The two categories that exist now correspond rather closely to the traditional notions of gerund and gerundive. However, this new stage of the historical development has never become the written norm. The written language basically sticks to the classical norm and continues to use the gerundive in complement

function, which should not be possible according to the new system. Therefore it seems advisable to proceed as above by taking the old system, which is very clearly reflected in the classical language, as the basis of the description and to treat as exceptions the uses that are due to the reanalysis.

5.3. The reanalysis in Hindi

Again in Hindi a quite parallel development is taking place. In less conservative variants of the language the unmarked masculine singular form -naa is used not only with [+masculine, +singular] direct objects and in the absence of any direct object, but also with other direct objects:¹¹

(51) (cf.33) māī roṭīī khaa-naa šuruu kar-taa hūū
(F) INF(.M.SG)

(52) (cf.34) voo kamr-ee deekh-naa caah-taa hai
PL INF(.M.SG)

So again an infinitive with adjectival properties becomes a perfectly normal, noun-like infinitive.

Interestingly, the infinitive in Hindi too derives historically from a future passive participle, as the late Latin declinable infinitive derives from the gerundive. According to a very plausible hypothesis, the naa-form continues the Sanskrit participle in -aṇiya- which had passive and modal meaning. Some residual instances of this original use can still be observed in Hindi:¹²

(53) kah-nii na kah-nii baat
say-INF.F.SG not say-INF.F.SG word(F)
"an improper word"

Likewise, there is an infinitive in -ba- in several modern Indoaryan languages (e.g. Gujarati) which historically derives from the other future passive participle of Sanskrit which was formed in -tava- (cf. Beames 1872-79, vol.III, p.236f. and p.152f.) This is additional evidence for our interpretation.

6. On the question of historical priority

By the above interpretation of the *nd*-form syntax and its reanalysis, we commit ourselves to an answer to the much-debated question of the historical priority of gerund or gerundive. After comparative philology in the 19th century had found in Osco-Umbrian something corresponding to the Latin gerundive, but nothing corresponding to the gerund, it became the prevalent opinion that the adjectival gerundive existed in Common Italic and consequently was primary with respect to the gerund, which was a later development of Latin. This view was challenged later, however, with syntactic arguments (see Aalto 1949, Tovar 1950, Hahn 1965, Blümel 1979, Stepanov 1985). The comparative-philological evidence was ignored or somehow explained away.

The semantic-syntactic relationship between the two uses of the gerundive (the predicative and the complement function) is indeed a problem, and we will return to it in more detail in the next section. In this context some remarks on the morphology seem in order. This issue has been "probablement la plus débattue de la morphologie latine" (Benveniste 1935), and we will confine ourselves to considering the relative plausibility of the two directions of derivation.

Those linguists who argued for the priority of the gerund for syntactic reasons regarded the gerundive as an "adjektiviertes Gerundium" (Aalto 1949: 147) have usually not been very explicit as to how exactly this adjectivalization may have taken place. In any event, it cannot be attributed to a word-formation process of the standard type. Tovar 1950 calls the relevant process, very vaguely, an "assimilation of the endings" in connection with a still vaguer "close relation between noun and adjective". Blümel's (1979:88) term here is the equally imprecise "attraction".

In fact, future passive participles are frequently derived from verbal nouns, but not by means of obscure "assimilation processes", but by the standard morphological means available in the language. There are numerous instances of such derivations

in other ancient Indo-European languages, as mentioned by Benveniste 1935:144 and again by Strunk 1977:33-34. For example, the Sanskrit future passive participles in *-aniya-* and *-tavya-*, mentioned in 5.3., are derived from infinitives in *-ana-* and *-tu-*. So we have to look in the same direction as Benveniste 1935:144-46, who explains Latin *-endo-* as a derivatin by means of the suffix *-do-* from an infinitive in *-er/en-*, and Risch 1984, who reconstructs an original **-tno-*, made up of the suffix *-tr/tn-* and the adjective-deriving suffix *-o-*.¹³

The gerund priority approach, then, cannot explain the identity of the morphology of both gerund and gerundive. Moreover, it cannot explain two important aspects of the syntax of the *nd*-form. First, the gerund has verbal government and modification; that is, objects in the genitive, dative, ablative (and later, accusative) cases and adverbs. Of course, the same is true for the infinitive, but the infinitive is not a (verbal) noun at all, as can be seen from the fact that it does not decline and can be governed only by verbs. A full-fledged verbal noun which can be declined and governed like any other noun would be expected to take its object in the genitive case and to take adjectival modifiers. On our analysis, the explanation is straightforward: the gerund is, in reality, a verbal adjective, which nobody would expect to show syntactic behavior other than it in fact shows. Second, as we have seen above (2.3.), the gerund does not occur in a position which is governed by a verb. In other words, it never occurs in the direct cases. This would be very odd behavior for an ordinary verbal noun, while on our interpretation it derives directly from the fact that the gerundive construction never occurs in this position.¹⁴

We conclude that a diachronic scenario with a verbal noun "gerund" at the start and a later development of a passive-modal verbal adjective "gerundive" is unacceptable for morphological and syntactic reasons.¹⁵ Moreover such a scenario would give us no possibility to account for the synchronic system of Latin in a unified way. Our analysis, however, not only provides such a unitary synchronic account, but is also completely in accord

with the diachronic data.

7. How can an adjective acquire propositional meaning?

7.1. The problem

If we account for the syntax of the Latin *nd*-form by reducing it to a passive verbal adjective, we have to explain the fact that this *nd*-form in certain constructions has complement function instead of attributive function and propositional instead of modifying meaning. As we have seen above (section 6.), many linguists have found this difficult and have instead tried to explain the adjectival use in terms of an original verbal noun. Unfortunately, this leads to serious conflicts with general syntactic and morphological considerations as well as with the comparative data.

Let us take a simple example of the gerundive construction:

- (54) *in persequendis hostibus*
in follow:GER:ABL.PL.M enemy(M):ABL.PL
"in following the enemy"

This looks like an ordinary NP with a modifying adjective and it should mean something like "in the enemy who is (going) to be followed". But in fact it means "in following the enemy". At first sight there seems to be no connection at all between these two meanings. But upon closer inspection we find that they are related in an interesting way. To show this, let us first consider a parallel within the same language.

There is another construction in Latin with very similar properties, the so-called "AUC" construction (cf., most recently, Bolkestein 1980). It looks like the gerundive construction with a past passive participle instead of the gerundive (hence it refers to past instead of present time). Examples:

- (55) *ab urbe condita*
from city(F)/ABL.SG found:PASTPTC:ABL.SG.F
"since the foundation of the city"

- (56) *ut expugnati oppidi famam antecederet* (Caes.bc 3,80,7)
COMP storm:PASTPTC:GEN.SG.N town(N):GEN.SG rumor arrive-before
"in order to arrive before the rumor of the storming of the town."
- (57) *cum patrem pulsum, patriam adflictam deploraret* (Cic.Sest.121)
COMP father:ACC.SG expel:PASTPTC:ACC.SG homeland:ACC.SG trouble:PASTPTC:ACC.SG deplore
"as he was sad that his father had been expelled and his country had got into trouble"
- (58) *Sardinia Siciliaque amissae*
Sardinia(F) Sicily(F):and lose:PASTPTC:NOM.PL.F
"the fact that Sardinia and Sicily have been lost"

As in the gerundive construction, these are NPs with propositional meaning whose head is not a verbal noun, but the underlying object. (55) literally means "from/since the founded city". Like the gerundive construction, the AUC construction is used predominantly in the indirect cases, but there are some exceptions like (58).

The similarity of the AUC construction and the gerundive construction has been noted by other linguists.¹⁶ Risch 1984:16 contrasts the AUC construction with the corresponding German construction. The following is a slightly modified version of his scheme.

The vertical arrows here mean that in the course of nominalization a constituent of the finite clause becomes the head of the resulting NP, while the horizontal arrows denote the dependency relations within the NP. It appears that Risch simply notes this difference between Latin and German without seeing any problem here. But there is a universal syntactic principle which states that in nominalizations of clauses the head of the clause (=the verb) becomes the head of the resulting NP.¹⁷

7.2. A cognitively-based approach

We would like to propose that one should look for a solution to the problem in cognitive rather than in syntactic principles.

Tovar 1950 comes close to it when he points out that "wir hier wieder einen Fall jener Verfahren vor uns haben, über die das Lateinische verfügt, um das Abstrakte durch das Konkrete auszudrücken." The normal case is that in a natural language "the abstract" (i.e. states of affairs) is expressed by an abstract noun when nominalized. Languages provide many different techniques of word formation and syntax which form nominalized constructions (mostly, NPs) from predicates that express states of affairs (verbs, adjectives).

On the other hand there is a cognitive principle that concrete things are more salient and easier to conceptualize than abstract states of affairs. Moreover, NPs typically denote things and not states of affairs, so that abstract NPs are rather untypical NPs. Such discrepancies between syntactic and cognitive principles, which are commonly "explained" by syntactic transformations, are discussed by Langacker 1984 within his framework of "Cognitive Grammar."

Langacker distinguishes in a state of affairs ("relational predication" in his terms) between the "active zone", that is those entities which participate in the state of affairs in the strict sense and the "profile", that is those entities which are conceptualized by the mind and expressed linguistically. In many cases active zone and profile coincide, but in many others they do not. For example, in (59)

(59) The woman heard the piano.

the active zone comprises only the auditory apparatus of the person and the sound that comes from the piano. But the person and the piano are much more salient for conceptualization¹⁹ and thus only they are profiled and expressed linguistically.

Similarly, discrepancies can arise in states of affairs which have other states of affairs (e.g. processes) as their participants. In (60) profile and active zone coincide ("to draw Cologne Cathedral").

(60) It is difficult to draw Cologne Cathedral.

In (61), however, the active zone is still the complete process "to draw Cologne Cathedral", but only its patient participant

is profiled.

(61) Cologne Cathedral is difficult to draw.

The relevant active zone is specified periphrastically with a to-infinitive here, but this periphrastic specification is not necessary. As Langacker observes, if the process functioning as the active zone is obvious from the context, the to-infinitive may be omitted. So in the context of a drawing class, (62) would be perfectly natural.

(62) Cologne Cathedral is difficult.

In certain cases such "illogical" conceptualizations can be regularized and become part of the grammar. So for cases such as (60)-(61) a syntactic transformation of "tough-movement" has been proposed.

7.3. Application to the gerundive

This account now easily transfers to the problem of the AUC and gerundive constructions. Here too participants are profiled although the active zone comprises the complete state of affairs. The predicate is then added attributively as a periphrastic specification of the active zone, in much the same way as it is added in the form of a to-infinitive in (61). But again as in (61), the periphrastic specification is not always obligatory. In (63)-(64), the (a) instances are complete gerundive or AUC constructions, while in the (b) instances the periphrastic specification has been omitted.

(63) (a) cupidi bellorum gerendorum (Cic.off.1,74)
 desirous wars(N):GEN.PL wage:GER:GEN.PL.N
 "desirous of waging war"

(b) cupidi bellorum
 "desirous of wars"

(64) (a) suspicio acceptae pecuniae (Cic.Verr.1,38)
 suspicion accept:PASTPTC:GEN.SG.F money(F):GEN.SG
 "the suspicion that money had been accepted"

(b) suspicio pecuniae
 "the suspicion of money"

Similar constructions can be found sporadically in other languages as well. Padučeva 1985 discusses this type of construction in Russian and gives the following examples:

- (65) (a) Bystro rastuščie ceny na toplivo podstegnuli interes
 quickly growing prices on fuel incite interest
 k ètoj probleme
 to this problem
 "The fast-rising fuel prices stimulated the interest in this problem."
 (b) bystryj rost
 quick growth
- (66) (a) Tol'ko malorasprostranennyj jazyk, na kotorom on pišet, mešaet
 only little-known language on which he writes prevents
 emu dostignut' v Evrope slavy lučšix anglijskix jumoristov.
 him attain in Europe fame best English humorists:GEN
 "Only the little-known language in which he writes
 prevents him from attaining in Europe the fame of the
 best English humorists."
 (b) malaja rasprostranennost' jazyka
 little knowness language:GEN

The literal translations of the (a) sentences seem quite natural in English too, and yet semantically and syntactically the more natural constructions are those given in (b).

The important difference between Russian (and English) on the one hand and Latin on the other is that in Russian such constructions occur only sporadically and no clear-cut syntactic rule can be given. Padučeva 1985 tries to formulate a number of general regularities for Russian but has great difficulty in pinning down the exact conditions. This is obviously due to the different status of such constructions in the grammars of different languages. In Russian they must be accounted for with reference to the above-mentioned cognitive principles, while in Latin they have been regularized to a greater degree (as in the case of the AUC construction) or completely syntacticized (=become part of the syntax) (as in the case of the gerundive construction).

7.4. Degrees of syntacticization

The preceding subsection shows that we have to distinguish between different degrees of syntacticization of cognitively-motivated constructions. In this respect, too, the constructions of attributive participles with propositional meaning are similar to the constructions involving tough-movement. Like the Latin gerundive construction, tough-movement in English has been syntacticized rather strongly. In other languages, this is not so.

Let us take Russian again. With adjectives like trudnyj "difficult", again either the process as a whole or its patient-participant alone may be profiled. Cf. (67), which is the more usual, and (68), which is acceptable in a suitable context:

- (67) Trudno narisovat' kël'nskij sobor.
 difficult draw Cologne cathedral
 "It is difficult to draw Cologne Cathedral."
 (68) Kël'nskij sobor truden.
 Cologne cathedral(M):NOM difficult:M
 "Cologne Cathedral is difficult."

The difference vis-à-vis English is that there is no easy or natural way of adding a periphrastic specification. (69) is possible, though it sounds rather odd stylistically. The specification here involves the verbal noun which shows various morphological and semantic idiosyncrasies and is thus itself much less regular than the English to-infinitive.

- (69) Kël'nskij sobor truden dlja risovanija.
 Cologne cathedral difficult for drawing
 lit. "Cologne Cathedral is difficult for drawing."

We see that Russian shows the same cognitively-motivated phenomenon, only in a lesser degree of syntacticization.

Thus, the gerundive construction may be explained as a particularly strongly syntacticized version of the same cognitively-motivated phenomenon that exists in other languages as well, but with less regularity. Still, the strong syntacticization of this type of construction in Latin is a rather peculiar thing and seems to be very rare across languages. In fact, I am not aware of any similar constructions except the Hindi infinitive.

Here, however, we can only infer that such a construction existed at some earlier time from the strange agreement pattern. Synchronically the infinitive is not a verbal adjective any longer (cf. note 6). It would be interesting to find a living example of a construction similar ^{to} that in Latin in some other language.²⁰

Notes

1. "The gerund fulfills the function of a verbal noun which supplements the infinitive in the oblique cases...and like the infinitive shows verbal government: legendi librum like legere librum... The gerundive is, according to the traditional view, a verbal adjective (similar to Greek φιλητέος) which was later integrated into the verbal system, like the to-participle."
2. I use the term "government" in the sense of Lehmann 1983, that is not in the sense of the Government and binding framework, where the subject is not included in the elements governed by the verb.
3. For this reason, the example of Hofmann & Szantyr, quoted above(2.2.), is quite misleading.
4. "The gerund is converted to the gerundive, i.e. the object stands in the case of the gerund and the gerundive is put in agreement with it:..."
5. There is a second infinitive in Hindi too, which has a much more restricted use. It is identical to the bare verb-stem and is used, e.g., as a complement of "be able" and forms part of the progressive aspect periphrasis:
 - (i) bacc-ee chat-par kheel sak-tee hai
child-PL roof-on play can-PRES COP.3.SG
"The children can play on the roof."
 - (ii) laṛkaa ghooree-koo maar rahaa hai
boy horse- OBJ strike PROG COP.3.SG
"The boy is striking the horse."
6. It should be noted, however, that, due to an earlier reanalysis in Hindi, the syntactic structure is as in the Russian example (32) and not as in the Latin example (38):

(i) mihi [nuntius] _{SUBJ} [mittendus est] _{PRED}	(=38)
(ii) mne [kupit' maslo] _{PRED}	(=32)
(iii) mujhee [khabar bheejnii hai] _{PRED}	(=37)

That is, whereas nuntius is the subject of the sentence in (i), khabar is the object of the infinitive in (iii), as is maslo in (ii). This is apparent from the facts of number agreement.

The finite verb does not agree in number with a plural object:

(iv) mujhee ciṭṭhi-yāṣṣ bheej-nii hai
to-me letter(F)-PL send - INF.F.PL COP.3.SG

"I have to send letters."

7. A terminology like the one proposed here is used in Aalto 1949.

8. "As is well-known, in classical Latin an accusative object is avoided with the gerund on the whole and instead the gerundive construction is used."

9. Risch's formulation reflects the expectation that it should be possible to use an accusative object with the gerund. On our analysis, of course, just the reverse is expected.

10. If we want to stick to our interpretation of the gerund as an impersonal passive in such cases, too, we have to allow for impersonal passives with accusative objects. The corresponding finite clause for the *nd*-phrase in (i) would look like (ii):

(i) te audiendi
you:ACC hear:GER:GEN(.SG.N) "of hearing you"

(ii) *te auditor
you:ACC is=heard lit. "*it is heard you"

(ii) is ungrammatical within the system of Latin, of course.

However, impersonal passives with accusative objects occur in other languages which are related to Latin genetically and typologically. A case in point is the Polish impersonal passive:

(iii) zaczął to taniec-Ø
begin - PASS.N dance - ACC
"Dancing was begun." lit. "It was begun dancing."

(iv) poda-no herbatę
serve - PASS.N tea - ACC
"Tea was served." lit. "It was served tea."

In Dutch such "transitive passives" occur in certain idioms (cf. Lange 1986):

(v) Er werd krokodillentranen gehuild.
there was crocodile-tears cried
"Crocodile tears were cried." lit. "It was cried crocodile tears."

These examples are intended to show that although transitive passives are not part of the system of Latin, they do occur in the language type that Latin belongs to. Therefore it is possible to assume a change in this direction for Latin, too, at least

in the restricted contexts indicated above. In any case, these are clear signs of the reanalysis which was to take place eventually.

11. Cf. Pořizka 1972:316.

12. Cf. Pořizka 1972:317.

13. This is not to deny the possibility that Latin *-ndo-* is a continuation of the Proto-Indo-European present passive (or "middle") participle in **-m(e)no-*. It is very well conceivable that the future or modal meaning developed later, and for the explanation of the gerundive construction (below, 7.3.) we need a simple present or future meaning anyway.

14. This, in turn, follows from the fact that the function of the gerundive construction was to supplement the infinitive in those positions where it could not appear (cf. 5.2., second paragraph). It was only secondarily a coding device for complementation and could never seriously compete with the infinitive. If Hahn's 1965 statement were correct that "(the infinitive) always 'competed' with the gerund so far as its inferior flexibility permitted", we would have to ask how the infinitive could possibly have survived in such an unequal struggle. In fact the infinitive was at no time challenged and survived from Proto-Indo-European to this day in most Romance languages.

15. There is only one real advantage of such an account. The fact that the gerundive is used very rarely in the attributive position with normal attributive meaning (*liber legendus* "a book that is to be read") is explained very easily if one assumes that the gerundive originated from the predicative position of the gerund. In our terms we have to assume that this normal attributive meaning fell into disuse as the gerundive construction became syntacticized more and more strongly. In any event, the existence of ancient adjectives like *secundus* "second" (old *nd*-form of *sequi* "follow") proves that the adjectival use of the *nd*-form dates back to prehistoric times.

16. That these two constructions were felt to be of similar status by Latin speakers is shown by examples like:

- (i) ante conditam condendam-ve urbem (Liv.praef.6)
before found:PASTPTC:ACC.SG.F found:GER:ACC.SG.F city(F):ACC.SG

"before the city had been founded or was in the process of being founded"

17. For example, Dik 1985:21 presents the following general schema for "adjustment of embedded predications to the pattern of nominal terms" (slightly simplified):

18. "Here again we are faced with a case of those techniques which Latin uses to express abstract ideas by means of concrete ones."

19. Langacker 1984:180 cites the following cognitive principles:

- (i) a whole is generally more salient than its individual parts;
- (ii) discrete physical objects are generally more salient than abstract entities;
- (iii) humans and (to a lesser extent) animals are generally more salient than inanimate objects (other things being equal)."

In (59), all of these are relevant: the auditory apparatus is both a part and inanimate, while the woman is a whole and human; the piano is a discrete physical object, while the sounds are more abstract entities.

20. Padučeva 1985:25 states that

"Zamena - fakul'tativnaja ili objazatel'naja - neksusnoj konstrukcii, kotoraja javljaetsja estestvennym sintaksičeskim oformleniem dlja podčinenoj predikacii, na junktivnuju izvestna vo mnogix jazykax."

("The -optional or obligatory - substitution of the nexus-construction, which is the natural syntactic form for a subordinate

predication, by the junction-construction in well-known in many languages.")

but to support this claim she gives examples only from Latin (both the AUC and the gerundive construction) and from Greek. For the AUC construction in Ancient Greek see Jones 1939. But note that this construction in Greek is not strictly parallel to the Latin construction because there is a three-way contrast:

- (i) (attributive:) hē hidroménē pólis
ART founded city
"the city which has been founded"
- (ii) (verbal noun:) hē tēs póleōs hídrusis
ART ART city:GEN foundation
"the foundation of the city"
- (iii) (AUC:) hē pólis hidroménē
ART city founded

The AUC construction is distinguished clearly from the attributive construction by the difference in word order. Therefore we have left the Greek case out of the present discussion. Nevertheless, this peculiar Greek construction deserves attention in connection with the general problems discussed here.

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